

HISTORY AND GEOGRAPHICAL PLACE OF MIRZACHOLIM

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Annatatsiya

Ushbu maqolada Mirzacho'l tumanining tashkil topishi ,uning geografik tuzulishi, iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy ahvoli , hozirgi kundagi ko'inishini yaqqol ochib beradi. Ayniqsa hozirgi kundagi “Yangi Mirzacho'l Tumani” tushunchalariga alohida to'htalib o'tilgan .Zamon talablariga javob beruvchi korxonalarining va fabrikalarning ochilishi ,ushbu ishlab chiqarish korxonalariga uyushmagan yoshlarni ish bilan taminlash muammolari yoritilib o'tilgan

Kalit so'zlar: Relyef,xo'jalik, zavod, iqtisodiyot,avtakorxonona,komissiya

Аннотация

В данной статье образование Мирзачульского района, его географическая структура, экономическое и социальное положение, наглядно раскрывает его нынешний облик. Особое внимание было уделено действующей концепции «Нового Мирзачульского района».

Ключевые слова: Рельеф, колхоз, завод, хозяйство, автозавод, комиссия.

Annotation

In this article , the formation of Mirzachul district, its geographical structure, economic and social situation, clearly reveals its current appearance. Special attention was paid to the current concept of "New Mirzachul District" .

Keywords: Relief , farm , factory, economy, auto plant, commission

Mirzachul district is a district of Jizzakh region. It was established on January 9, 1967. It borders Kazakhstan to the north, Syrdarya region to the northeast, Dostlik district of Jizzakh region to the south, Forish and Arnasay districts to the west. Area 0 , 42 thousand km². Population 52,400 people (2020). Mirzachul district has 1 city (Gagarin), 8 rural communities (Gardener, Ipakyoli, Mirzadala, Pakhtazor, Tashkent, Yangidala, Uzbekistan, Gulzor). The center is the city of Gagarin

Nature - the relief of Mirzachul district (depending on the appearance, size, origin, age and history of development on the surface, ocean and seabed) is lowland. The climate is sharply continental, dry, cold in winter and hot in summer. The average temperature is -1.5 ° in January and 30 ° in July; minimum temperature —30 ° (January), maximum temperature 42 ° (July). The vegetation period is 224 days . The average annual rainfall is 240 mm. The soil is light gray and sandy. Wild plants include brown-headed, wormwood, sagebrush, sagebrush,

sagebrush, sagebrush, sagebrush, reed, sagebrush, asparagus, sagebrush, sagebrush, sagebrush, poplar, willow, and others. Wild animals include rabbits, tuvalaks, foxes, and chiyabors; from rodents rats, rattlesnakes, field mice; reptiles include tortoises, snakes, lizards, birds include desert eagles and wild ducks.

Economy - The district economy is mainly specialized in agriculture. There are industrial, transport, communications and construction enterprises. He is engaged in cotton growing, grain growing, gardening and cattle breeding. There are small, private businesses in the district. The total area under crops in Mirzachul district is 28.2 thousand hectares, including 13.8 thousand hectares of cotton, 11 thousand hectares of cereals, 1.2 thousand hectares of legumes, 321 hectares of melons. There are farmers, collective farms, fattening farms and 9 company farms. There is a main railway through the district. There are Syrdarya-Jizzakh, Yettisay district of Kazakhstan-Pakhtakor, Gulistan-Gagarin highways. In addition, Mirzachul district has a car plant, a gin, a rental company, joint stock companies, trade, cultural and consumer services. There are 20 general secondary schools (more than 4,200 students), vocational schools, 11 clubs, 11 libraries, 4 cultural and recreational parks, 7 stadiums, and monuments. There are 4 hospitals, 3 non-governmental medical institutions, 5 rural outpatient clinics, 2 obstetrics and feldshers, 10 pharmacies. As you can see, our district meets the needs of the population with its modern enterprises.

“Yangi Mirzachul district” (Obod Mirzachul) - Almost 70 years ago, in order to build new settlements, villages, housing estates for the population, employment and living on the sands of Uzbekistan. In order to create conditions, desert deserts were developed. Water was brought with a thousand hardships. Buildings were built, modern facilities, first of all, socio-cultural and residential facilities were built in a short time. In Mirzachul district of Jizzakh region, such large-scale work was carried out and our brothers came to help not only from our republic, but also from neighboring countries. Later they settled in these beautiful corners. The multi-ethnic Mirzachul district has been inhabited for many years as a brother, sister-in-law and cousin. However, the passing years have not gone unnoticed in the region. Because the buildings that have been built have been worn out for 70 years. Unfortunately, the barracks, which were temporarily built for builders and workers at that time, were not renovated. Built of ordinary wood, the house, the foundation of which is intended only for a few years, serves as a permanent refuge for people. In the late 80s, the houses gradually began to light up. The appeal above only ended with the answer "wait."

Thankfully, the chest pain in the district has gone away. In order to radically renew the architectural appearance of rural settlements, integrated development of regions, construction of road and transport infrastructure, engineering and communication networks and social facilities, and in this way to improve the living standards of the population in March 2018, the President said. The adoption of the decree and the decision of the President of the Republic of Tajikistan have solved the problems that have accumulated in Mirzachul district for many years. According to the decision, in the first place, a Special Commission was formed. A local roadmap was drawn up and tasks were set in order to radically improve the situation, with a full and detailed study of the current situation by members of the commission, which includes officials, sector leaders and members of the public from about 30 organizations. The structure of the commission is as great as listening to the hearts of the people, providing practical assistance in solving their problems, working hard to implement the principles of working based on the needs and desires of the people in our lives. 'goal-oriented. In order to carry out these tasks, they visited 1,405 apartments on 17 streets in the Galaba mahalla and studied the existing problems. Shortcomings in the field of utilities, housing, employment, household services, more than a thousand cases of correcting the necessary documents have been identified, most of which have been resolved on the spot. Keeping up with the times is the solution to our main problem. Many of these appeals are related to the housing issue, as noted above. For this reason, the citizens were very pleased that in accordance with the instructions of the President, instead of barracks and unsightly houses in this neighborhood will be built one-storey two- and three-room houses on a plot of 4 hundred square meters on 400 standard projects.

It must be acknowledged that the houses built under the renovated projects are not similar in Central Asia in terms of their price parameters, quality characteristics and comfort. The fact that such houses were first given to the population living in 54 houses that had no conditions for many years added to the joy of the homeowners. One of them is the Norkuziyev family. Six years ago, the landlord died in an accident. Four children were left screaming. The housewife took care of the household. But the lack of work in the area, and the fact that the house was about to collapse, broke the hearts of family members. Even the eldest child of the family, a college graduate Nilufarkhan, did not knock on many doors in search of work. Unfortunately, he could not find any work and was in a state of panic. At present, these problems are being solved and the burden of the population is being lightened.

The scope of work is really wide. A radical turning point began in Mirzachul's life. The cause of indifference turned the desert into a desert, and in a fading district, life began again. Just as a quarter of a century ago people were eager to improve the area, today thousands of our compatriots are trying to reach Mirzachul. The joy of creativity in the hearts, the blood flowing in the veins of young people, everyone is working on one goal, one idea - "to turn Mirzachol into a flower garden."

It is impossible not to dwell on what is happening here one by one. First of all, housing is necessary for the population to live well, to live a peaceful and happy life. With this in mind, great attention was paid to the construction of affordable housing in the region on the basis of standard projects. Construction of 112 new houses has begun. Trenches were dug in 48 additional houses under construction and shiben was laid in 110 houses.

and means of the FVV system , hundreds of special equipment and devices, specialists and manpower were mobilized in this work. About 600 soldiers from the military units of the ministry system were solemnly welcomed. Their arrival further increased the pace of work here. The selfless work of young, energetic young men has changed the attitude of others to work as well. They are working hard to build these houses . An additional 400 troops are expected to arrive in the coming days . This will further increase the pace of landscaping in the region. It is noteworthy that the residents of the neighborhood, in particular, more than 500 people are involved in landscaping. The goal is to build a prosperous place faster. With their efforts, 54 multi-storey houses in the neighborhood are becoming more beautiful day by day. The roofs of all the houses have been completely renovated. The old unusable slates were replaced with new ones. The turn came to the facades of the houses. The wind of the " Prosperous Village" program has reached here as well. News on drinking water and sewage supply is also encouraging. For example , 9.5 km of drinking water network has been laid and now 6 km of pipes have been laid. A 400-meter trench has been dug and a total of 3,850 meters of pipe has been laid to date. A total of 68 existing sewerage wells in the region have been cleaned. 12 new kolodets were brought. Cleaning of 2 out of 4 existing sewerage wells has been completed. Sewage networks 100 meters of trenches were dug in front of multi -storey houses, 300 meters of sewers were brought, 3 sewer wells were installed. Our road workers are also fulfilling the task assigned to them. To date, they have laid a total of 483 pieces of 2898 meters of new trays, 590 tons of concrete, 2050 tons of sand and gravel. Every year the

population's demand for natural gas is growing . The problem of natural gas in this district has not been solved for years. Under the program, this shortcoming will also be addressed . 15.0 km of gas pipelines were dismantled and gas supply in the region was improved . 570 liquefied gas cylinders were distributed to the residents of the remote area.

and construction waste were transported per day, and 23,000 tons since the beginning of the season .

By the way, it is difficult to find households in the village that do not raise livestock. However , this is not possible in multi -storey houses. Until now, however, residents of apartment buildings in the Galaba neighborhood have struggled to raise livestock due to a lack of facilities. Due to the lack of space, illegal, non-compliant barns were built around it like a spider's web. In the framework of the "Prosperous Village" program, taking into account this good work, the construction of a modern building for the storage of livestock and fodder on the outskirts of the neighborhood is in full swing.

In Mirzachul district, too, the employment of able-bodied people, taking into account the employment of college graduates has become a problem for years. This is due to the fact that in the district, except for a small number of small businesses, there are no centers for the service sector, manufacturing enterprises. The citizens in the vortex of the problem did not find a way to solve it. This important issue has also been taken into account in the work of the program. A 200-seat sewing workshop and Mirzachul Text factories worth \$ 9 million will be launched in the center of the district. It is planned to involve 250 women and young people in the production of export-oriented products. Currently, construction work is underway on the 12-hectare area allocated for the factory .

Seeing these changes, it was once said, "You were a desert, turned into a desert . Thank you, man." In short, the creative work that began in Mirzachul has brought prosperity to the hearts of the people . .

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